

BASES OF HINDU CULTURE: PHILOSOPHICAL SCHOOLS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO WORLD SPIRITUALITY

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

Hindu culture is one of the oldest and most complete philosophical structures with spiritualist purpose formulated in the history of mankind. Recognized for its depth, complexity and breadth of reasoning, which virtuously associates the scientific root with spiritual subjects in explanations about manifestation and divine reality. This article, whose general objective is to present the bases on which this philosophical-cultural system, and its structure of thought, was based, and, for specific objectives, to demonstrate how it contributed to the formulation of the main religions and philosophies of the world, which aim to help man to re-find his true nature. As a methodology, a bibliographic research was carried out that covered both Western authors, researchers of culture and philosophy of the East, as well as Eastern authors, renowned for their explanation about the studies of the Hindu tradition. It was found that the works that explain the influence of the ancient structure of eastern philosophical and scientific thought, especially the Hindu tradition, present the depth

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and dedication that this theme requires and evidences the need for continuity and expansion of the study carried out.

Keywords: Eastern Philosophy, Hinduism, Hindu Culture, Hindu Philosophical Schools, *Dárshanas*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Therefore, no other place has given world spirituality as great a contribution as India. More than any other people, the Indians showed incredible spiritual versatility, which inspired many other nations and gave, in this twentieth century of ours, much needed help to Western civilization, so deficient in the things of the Spirit. (FEUERSTEIN, 2006, p. 99).

Hindu culture is one of the oldest and most complete philosophical structures of spiritualist thought and behavior formulated in the history of mankind. In the words of Mircea Eliade, "India applied itself with unparalleled rigor to the analysis of the various conditionings of the human being" (ELÍADE, 2009, p. 12). Its roots are founded on the ancient Indian civilization, with more than 10,000 years of existence, formerly called *Maha Bharata*[3], or Greater India, which flourished on the outskirts and tributaries of the Indo and Saraswati rivers and on the slopes of the Himalayas. It was the largest and oldest civilization on the planet, even compared to Egyptian, Mesopotamian or Chinese civilizations. (AUBOYER and AYMARD, 1965; MATTOSO, 1956; FEUERSTEIN, 2006)

Its philosophical-cultural system remains virtually unchanged in its essence to this day, persisting for centuries of insistent invasions and domains by different peoples - among which are the Persians, Greeks, white Huns, Arabs and Europeans, quoting only a few - and remains firmly consolidated in the identity of the Indian people and Hindus around the world.

The strength of this culture lies in its dedication to a real perquisition for universal Truth and the Divine Essence behind every manifestation, as well as in the conviction that the achievement of this knowledge is given by the human condition. The appreciation for all sincere paths aimed at the awareness of this spiritual reality

confirms that Hindu culture has in ecumenism and in the versatility of thought its philosophical-spiritual basis. Therefore, it accepts, in its essence, all philosophies and religions as real paths for the encounter with the Divine Essence, "for the development and fulfillment of human destiny on earth" (GAMA and LIMA, 2019). These findings highlight the fact that Hindu culture does not have a founder, a foundation date, or a centralizing institution (GAMA and LIMA, 2019).

Even before it is recognized as a religion, the Hindu cultural tradition is a consolidated philosophy of life, called since the times of *Sanatana Dharma*, a Sanskrit term meaning the "Eternal Way" or the "Eternal Law", taught by the oral tradition (*Paramparay*) from master to disciple, from father to son, from generation to generation, even before it is even written or codified.

In this sense, this article has as its general objective to present the bases on which this philosophical-cultural system was based. Based on an ethical search, Hindu Culture highlights the spiritual maturity achieved, recognized for its depth, complexity and breadth of reasoning, which provides substantial contributions to science and global ecumenism (ZIMMER, 2003; FEUERSTEIN, 1975).

Likewise, it has as its specific objectives, to demonstrate that most of the philosophical schools of the planet originated in the *Sanatana Dharma*, which provided humanity with the great legacy of spirituality associated with a living scientific root. Ancient India was the birthplace and abode of great sages (*Rishis*[4]) and illustrious messiahs, as well as great revelations of ancient and modern science, sung in the *Vedas*[5], as well as in the *Upanishads* and *Itihásas*[6] (epics), described in the *Smritis* (codes of law), *Puránas* (legends and parables), *Dárshanas* (philosophical schools or points of view) and *Shastras*[7] (scriptures) of each area of science and the arts. Therefore, this ancient culture is also called *Hindu Rishi* or *Yoga Rishi*.

As a methodology, a bibliographical research was carried out that covered both Western authors, recognized researchers of culture and philosophy of the East, such as Gama (2011 and 2019) Elíade (2009) and Feuerstein (2006); as Eastern authors,

renowned for their explanation of the studies of the Hindu tradition, ranging from spiritualistic bases to scientific foundations, such as Sivananda (2013a), Yogananda (2010 and 2011) and Tigunait (2011).

It was found that the works that explain the influence of the ancient structure of eastern philosophical and scientific thought, especially the Hindu tradition, present the depth and dedication that this theme requires and evidences the need for continuity and deepening of the study carried out.

2. THE FOUNDATIONS OF HINDU CULTURE

2.1 HINDU CULTURE AND THE SEARCH FOR UNIVERSAL TRUTH

Hindu is not a mere name. The Hindu name is not only geographical, but also of national and racial importance. The whole history of our nation from the beginning is connected to it. All our ideas and ideals are so intimately connected to him that it is difficult to give a simple definition of it. (SIVANANDA, 2013a, p. 23, our translation).

The name "Hindu" has its foreign origin, given by the Persians who came to call the population living on the banks of the great Indo River "Hindus", as well as "Sindhus" by the Greeks. And so the Hindu name became known in the West to refer to the residents of ancient India (TIGUNAIT, 2011, p.05). The original name given by the inhabitants was always *Bharata* or *Maha-Bharata*.

During the British government, the term Hinduism was often used also to differentiate, in strictly religious terms, the followers of the Hindu and Muslim religions. Thus, the restriction on adopting the religious character, to the detriment of the cultural dimension of the name Hinduism is a Western heritage. As a spiritualist philosophy, more and more people on all continents are adopted and currently have more than 1 billion adherents (PEW RESERCH CENTER, 2012).

In India, culture, philosophy, science and religion are always integrated, guide and elucidating all aspects of life, laws, moral order, customs, rituals and social

organization, and still constitutes a millenary way of life, which is reinvigorated and renewed with each new generation (HINDUISM TODAY, 2007).

The civilization of the Indo-Saraswati River Valley or Harappan[8] civilization was the society that lived and developed Hindu culture, and corresponds to one of the largest and oldest civilizations that man has known[9] (FEUERSTEIN, 2006). A very sophisticated and advanced culture and, at the same time, extremely simple and functional, visible aspects in the great organization and cohesion between the different cities implanted in a vast territory, with extensive networks of communication and commerce (FEUERSTEIN, 2006, p. 143).

This civilization built cities, temples, streets, roads, large barns and urban infrastructure systems with a much more advanced technical and comprehensive capacity than that achieved in the 19th century.C. in the Western world. It was from the archaeological finds that many questions about the origin of Hinduism were answered. The traditional residents, known as the Dravidiano people, already had a wide set of cultural aspects and material artifacts dating back to the Hindu tradition known today (ELÍADE, 2009, p. 292).

"The Hindu *Vedas* proclaim "*Ekam Sat, Viprah Bahudha Vêdanti*": there is a truth, only men describe it in different ways." (VISWANATHAN, 2015, our translation).

Hindu culture is founded on the unwavering pursuit of universal Truth, always existing and permanently accessible to all who seek It, even if they ignore hindu scriptures or ideals. Thus, it does not project itself as the only path to spiritual fulfillment, as it does not claim the exclusive ownership of knowledge (SIVANANDA, 2013b; VIVEKANANDA, 2007). "Whatever the way in which one can seek God, it is always in God's way" (VISWANATHAN, 2015, our translation).

Hinduism is full of all kinds of ideas and thought structures. If on the one hand, one can find, the highly spiritualist *Vêdânta* and *Mimânsa*, on the other, identifies the philosophy *Sâmkyá*, highly realistic or "the *Charvaka* highly materialistic, atheistic and hedonistic, who does not believe in God or the *Vedas*" (VISWANATHAN, 2015,

our translation). Both idolatry is considered part of Hinduism, as philosophical lines that do not recognize any idol.

Hindu philosophical schools (*Dárshanas*) were formulated, intensely debated to provide a broad and systematic method for each man to explore his inner potentials and then achieve the supreme consciousness inherent in his own existence.

There is and has been in India something that is indeed philosophy. (...) Its objectives are precisely those that inspired high philosophical flights of thinkers such as those of the pre-Socratic period: Parmenides, Empédocles, Pythagoras and Heraclitus (ZIMMER, 2003, p. 37 and 38).

The questions about the manifestation, the formation of the universe or the divine Reality permeate a logical and scientific maturity, whose structure undertook above all the construction of western philosophy and science (ZIMMER, 2003).

2.2 PERSISTENT TRANSMISSION OF KNOWLEDGE THAT HAS ALWAYS EXISTED

Hinduism is as old as the world itself. Hinduism is the mother of all religions. The Hindu scriptures are the oldest in the world, Sanatana-Dharma is so called, not only because it is eternal, but also because it is protected by God and because it can make us eternal. (SIVANANDA, 2013a, p. 18, our translation).

Countless studies attest to the timeless character of Hindu consciousness and culture (SIVANANDA, 2013a; FEUERSTEIN, 2006; ZIMMER, 2003). It can be said that it is the oldest culture, philosophy and religion in the world. The knowledge to which it refers has always existed in India and has been incorporating elements of the invading peoples, but it also fed them with extensive scientific and spiritual knowledge (VISWANATHAN, 2015; SIVANANDA, 2013a).

India is revealed, especially at the religious, conservative level par excellence: almost none of its immemorial heritage was lost. We better understand this fact by examining the relations between the Proto-historical civilizations of the Indo and contemporary Hinduism. (ELÍADE, 2009, p. 290).

Hinduism began with *Shruti*, a Sanskrit word meaning "that which is heard" or "divine revelation", understood by *Rishis* who lived in time immemorial and who heard the eternal Truths, transmitting them to the world. Each branch of knowledge is associated with a highly specialized art and science and a congruent way of life, so learning is done alongside a master (*Guru*) who teaches with his own example, because it brings with him the ability to understand the nature of divine manifestation.

For the Hindu, every individual is a *Sukshma-Jagat*, that is, a "miniature world", corroborating the Christian idea that God created man in His image and likeness (Genesis 1:26 and 27, In: KJA, 2016, p. 31). Thus, self-knowledge is a sure way to find its own divine essence (*Purusha*), because by understanding its own internal forces, it will be able to understand all the forces of nature and the universe.

It is in this sense that one understands why religious intolerance is the main enemy of spirituality and has not only been responsible for many crimes against humanity, driving man's distancing from a true spiritual search (SARMA, 1967, p. 121).

The history of India, both in antiquity and later, was characterized by a virtually continuous state of foreign invasions, without there being loss in its philosophical and spiritual depth. Hindu culture is a tradition that has enormous strength to overcome the barriers of time, influences, invasions and impositions (KRISHNANANDA, 1997 and 2012).

According to Krishnananda (2012, p. 15), one of the reasons presented is that "behind this persistence of India's culture lies its capacity for accommodation, which does not reject the ideals of the past and does not ignore the ideals that can advance in the future." The power of absorption and assimilation of Hindu culture is so great that even a religious tradition clearly defined as Christianity was involved by Indian culture (FEUERSTEIN, 2006, p. 101). The apostle of Jesus, St. Thomas, migrated to India to transmit the Christian teachings, remained in India until his death.

The Greek army of Alexander III of Macedonia, known as Alexander the Great, entered the Indian subcontinent in 325 BC.C., ruling for a short period of time, did not

pass the River Hifasis (present-day Beas River), and did not enlarge his Empire for India, as occurred with the Persian invasions and the white Huns. It can be stated above all that the Greeks and Romans absorbed hindu knowledge and thought structures to formulate their own cultural traditions, which formed the structural foundations of Western civilization. (MUKUNDCHARANDÁS, 2011)

Ecumenical India still gave rise to many missionaries who migrated to the West[10] teaching respect, ecumenism, as true values of their own belief. Hindu culture has taught humanity that ethics takes a deeper action on existence and that it should be reflected in culture as an essential value of social life (KRISHNANANDA, 2012, p. 38).

2.3 PHILOSOPHICAL BASIS FOR THE WORLD'S MAJOR RELIGIONS AND PHILOSOPHIES

O Arjuna, whenever virtue (*dharma*) declines and vice (*adharma*) predominates, I incarnate myself as an Avatar. In visible form I appear, from the age to the age, to protect the virtuous and destroy evil in order to restore virtue. (YOGANANDA, 2010, p. 283, note n^o. 09).

The vast majority of mankind has placed their lives at the feet of great prophets, illustrious scholars, considered divine incarnations that have formed the souls of the world's major religions and philosophies throughout history. Each prophet was and is a necessity of his own time, "the embodiment of what is best and greatest in his people - the meaning, the life for which this people has fought since time immemorial; and he himself is the impetus for the future, not only for his own nation, but for countless nations of the world" (YOGANANDA, 2010, p. 320).

India was the birthplace and place of study, passage and abode of great sages that mankind has known. Siddhartha Gautama the Buddha was an Indian prince (500 a.C.), leader of the Sakya Clan, who abdicated the comfort of his kingdom to devote himself to spiritual search. Upon reaching Enlightenment (*Samádhi*), he committed his life to transmitting to the world the wisdom found. Buddhism currently has more than 500 million adherents worldwide (PEW RESERCH CENTER, 2012).

Like Siddhartha, Jesus Christ lived in India, living with great scholars (*Rishis*), from whom he received teachings and performed spiritual practices, until he awakened his path to spiritual Truth, and thus returned to his homeland to teach the wisdom found (KERSTEN, 2018). It can be said that the ideals taught by Christ are the same as in the scriptures of India, analogous to the highest possible teachings, which existed long before his coming[11], a new expression of the *Sanatana Dharma* (YOGANANDA, 2010, p. 280, and 281). Currently the Christian tradition has more than 2 billion adherents (PEW RESERCH CENTER, 2012).

Mahavira (600 d.C.), also known as Vardhamana, founder of the Jain religious-spiritualist tradition, currently with about 4 million followers (PEW RESERCH CENTER, 2012), was a great Indian sage and like Siddhartha, who came out of the comfort of his family environment to devote himself to spiritual life. Similarly, Nanak, born in the Indian subcontinent in 1469, was the founder of Sikismo, one of the world's oldest religions, today with more than 23 million followers (PEW RESERCH CENTER, 2012).

The great master Bodhidharma, who was born in India in the 5th century, spread the teachings of Hindu culture in China, where he lived until his death. And in this period, it was widely recognized by the teaching of martial arts (*Vajramushti*), not only in Shaolin, but throughout the continent (SIVANANDA, 2013c).

We find Hindu references in myths, legends, parables, and scriptures of every order in the world's leading civilizations and peoples. According to Yogananda (2010), we find both in the book Genesis, in the Ten Commandments of Moses, in legends and rituals of the Bible, as well as in the miracles performed by Christ a "parallel with the hereafter seen literature of India. The teachings of Christ in the New Testament and Krshnaa in the *Bhagavad Gita* have an exact correspondence" (YOGANANDA, 2010, 281).

In addition, in the field of science, the great achievements of Hindu masters are recognized. The exquisite grammatical structure of the Sanskrit language, one of the oldest in the world, known as *Devanágari*, is considered the mother tongue and has

influenced languages throughout the planet, such as English, Latin, Greek, French, etc. (GAMA and YAMADA, 1996). It was coded by the wise Panini in 1600 bc.C. Added to this, that Divodas Dhanvantari transmitted the teachings of medicine and surgery in 1,000 a.C., long before the discovery in the West. Together with Sushruta, who lived at the same time, they are recognized as the fathers of medicine in the world, followed by Charak, who lived in the mid-800s.C. (SIVANANDA, 2013c).

Aryabhata (476 d.C.) was one of the first and leading astronomers and mathematicians, the first man who transmitted the teachings of algebra and astronomy with enormous precision, on a date long before the discovery acclaimed by the Western people. He was accompanied by the astronomer Varahamihir (499 d.C.), who described the forces of gravity more than a millennium before Isaac Newton (1,670 d.C.). Also known is Baskaracharya (1114 d.C.), who was a genius of algebra, arithmetic and geometry, whose writings inspired Persian and Greek travelers and influenced Western science and philosophy (MUKUNDCHARANDÁS, 2011).

Hindus were instrumental in revealing the Truth and emphasizing the importance of this search, whether by scientific, rational, devotional, or spiritualist means, and influenced schools around the planet. These facts are emphasized if we take into account that, about five thousand years ago, "when the ancestors of Britons and Gauls, greeks and Latinos, roamed the immense forests of Europe in search of food, in full barbarism, Hindus were already dedicated to meditating on the mystery of life and death." (YOGANANDA, 2011, p. xii).

2.4 SCIENTIFIC AND PHILOSOPHICAL ROOT OF HINDU SPIRITUALITY

It is understood that for Hindu thought the fundamental problem of all philosophy, science and art is the search for Truth. However, "Truth is not valuable in itself; it becomes fundamental because the knowledge of truth helps man to free himself" (ELÍADE, 2009, p. 19), is the recognition of the laws of nature and that govern its

evolution. For the Hindu, the cause of human suffering is due to ignorance (*Avidya*) of its divine essence.

If on the one hand, the conception of science by the West is a commonly anti-religious and non-spiritualist view of man and the universe; for the East, the material and spiritual reality, manifest and unmanifest, coexist in interaction. Western science separately knowledge into disciplines, while for the eastern thought structure everything is permanently connected and interrelated and there is no way to be understood in its fullness in isolation, as can be understood in the formulation of Hindu philosophical schools (*Dárshanas*) (TAGORE, 1931).

Most Hindu philosophical systems integrate metaphysics, epistemology, logic, cosmology, aesthetics, ethics, sociology, psychology and physiology. Disciplines are always interrelated, especially in a theoretical and practical way. And if there is no application in life effectively, it is not considered philosophy at all. The deep study of a discipline will undeniably bring the understanding of the other. The part cannot be separated from the whole without loss (GAMA and LIMA, 2019; TIGUNAIT, 2011). The integrality acclaimed by Hindu scholars has led to a scientific depth that modern science still gropes, as with quantum physics, string theory, genetics and cosmology, for example.

The history of violence and aggression on religious grounds, such as the case of the persecution of heretics by the Catholic Church or the war waged by radical Muslims to this day, explain the reasons why Giordano Bruno or Descartes, for example, preached the liberation of rational thought, previously attached to religious dogma. However, it should be noted that in India there has never been a radical clash between science and religion. Hindu philosophy has remained traditional and renewed, so that science and religion have strengthened and helped each other, from ancient times to the present day.

The starting point of the philosophical reflection of the Eastern tradition is the real limit of human capacity for reasoning and logic. According to Tagore (1931), the universe described by man is circumscribed to the common human reality, just as the

scientific view is also limited to the scientific mind of man. However, the author warns of the human potential of understanding the Truth, in which "the pattern of reason and appreciation that gives him access to truth is the pattern of the Eternal Man, the One who experiences through our experience" (TAGORE, 1931, p. 203), corroborating the human potential of access to divine Reality.

The second starting point is that Truth is one with the Universal Being, and it is indifferent if it reaches it through philosophical, scientific or spiritualist inquiry. For the Hindu, the primordial reality must also be investigated and questioned to be understood by the mind of man.

The *Vedas* are considered the main source of all Hindu culture and wisdom, from which philosophical speculations lead to the *Vêdânta*, forms of devotion lead to *Bhakti* doctrine, rituals and sacrifices lead to studies of the *Mimânsa* school, questions about creation lead to *Sâmkyá* cosmology, practical descriptions lead to the *Sádhana* of *Yoga*, and logic and reasoning research introduces *Nyáya* and *Vaishêshika* science. All cry out for the rescue of the principles of the Truth, to the detriment of the ritualistic somuch of meaning and content.

It is almost impossible to define when and how Hindu philosophical schools (*Dárshanas*) were originally formulated or even calculate their influence on the foundation of so many solid systems around the world. It is known that a spirit of philosophical and scientific inquiry sung in a pure way in the *Vedas*, was already in force in the days of the first *Upanishads*. These are systematic studies, written in *sutras*[12], the result of reliable oral transmissions.

With high esteem and respect, the speculations of each philosophical school were reconciled with doctrines of the existing systems, placed under criticism and analysis that gave rise to the numerous comments, texts as important as the originals of each *Dárshana*. In Hindu tradition, it is necessary to recognize the growth that each school has acquired over time, as there is no place for schools that have had their importance only for a certain period.

Rationalist schools, such as *Sámkhyá*, *Nyáya* or *Vaisheshika*, strongly influenced Western thinkers such as Pythagoras, Socrates and Aristotle, and contributed to the supply of knowledge to the oldest libraries such as Alexandria, for example, which formed the basis of Western logical and rational thought understood today as science or philosophy.

2.5 HINDU PHILOSOPHICAL SCHOOLS (DÁRSHANAS)

2.5.1 NYÁYA: KNOWLEDGE THROUGH LOGIC

The philosophical school *Nyáya*, codified by the sage Shri Gautama in 600 a.C., also known as *Aksapada Vidya*, is applied in describing the conditions, validity and nature of the correct knowledge (*Vidya*), as well as the means to acquire it. The Sanskrit word *Nyáya* means "logic, method" or "critical study science". Thus, it is recognized for highlighting reason, logic and systematic reasoning as a real instrument of knowledge (GAMA, 2011, p. 72). It formed the basic structure of reasoning and logic of Eastern philosophy, especially for other Hindu and world philosophical schools. Its main coding is contained in the *Nyáya Sutra* of *Shri Gautama*, as well as in the comments *Vatsyayana Bhasya* of *Vatsyayana* (500 a.C.).

It is essential to point out again that, in hindu tradition, writing arose on a date far superior to the transmission and organization of teaching. The *Paramparay* system, described earlier, of oral transmission kept for millennia fidelity and purity long before the need for coding and elaboration of analyses and comments.

The *Nyáya* system studies the manifest and unmanifest realities for the search for knowledge, called *Prameya*, detailed in Chart 1, which means "what can be known" or "object of true knowledge", not necessarily found in the physical world. It is important to point out that the word comes from the Sanskrit root "*Prama*" meaning "superior knowledge", and refers to everything that is to be known in Reality, not just material or circumscribed in the universe of the senses.

Table 1 - Objects of Knowledge (*Prameya*)

1. Alma (<i>Atman</i>)	7. Atividade (<i>Pravriti</i>)
2. Corpo (<i>Sharira</i>)	8. Defeito mental (<i>Dosa</i>): 8.1. Apego (<i>Raja</i>), 8.2. Ódio (<i>Dvesa</i>), 8.3. Paixão ou ilusão (<i>Moha</i>),
3. Cinco sentidos (<i>Indriyas</i>)	9. Renascimento (<i>Pretyabhava</i>)
4. Objetos dos sentidos (<i>Artha</i>)	10. Frutos ou resultados (<i>Phala</i>)
5. Cognição (<i>Buddhi</i>)	11. Sofrimento (<i>Dukha</i>)
6. Mente (<i>Manas</i>)	12. Completa liberdade do sofrimento (<i>Apavarga</i>)

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

According to Gama (2011, p. 73), one of the main contributions of the *Nyáya* system, accepted and adopted by all other philosophical schools, is the concept of *Pramana*, the valid or true source of knowledge, accurate in Chart 2. The word also has as meaning the concepts of "measure, limit, (...) authority, testimony, evidence, instrument or means of knowledge" (BLAVATSKY, 2012, p. 567)

In a logical and rational way, this school describes each of the sources of knowledge, a concept also a fundamental part of the *Sámkhyá* naturalist school. The acuity of each stage of analysis of the *Nyáya* system requires discernment, precision and philosophical depth to be considered true or real.

Table 2 - Sources of valid knowledge (*Pramana*)

1. Percepção (<i>Pratyaksa</i>)	1.1. Ordinário (<i>Laukika</i>)	
	1.2. Indeterminado (<i>Nirvikalpa</i>)	
	1.3. Extraordinário (<i>Alaukika</i>)	1.3.1. Classes (<i>Samanyalaksana</i>)
		1.3.2. Associação (<i>Jñanalaksana</i>)
		1.3.3. Intuição (<i>Yogaja</i>)
2. Inferência (<i>Anumana</i>)	1.4. Declaração (<i>Pratijñā</i>)	
	1.5. Razão (<i>Hetu</i>)	
	1.6. Exemplo (<i>Udaharana</i>)	
	1.7. Proposição universal (<i>Upanaya</i>)	
	1.8. Conclusão (<i>Nigamana</i>)	
3. Comparação ou analogia (<i>Upamana</i>)		
4. Testemunho autorizado (<i>Shabda</i>)		

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

It can be said that valid knowledge is one that corresponds to the real nature of the object and corresponds with the facts, otherwise it is considered invalid. By limiting the human mind, knowledge remains incomplete and invalid knowledge generally prevails. Therefore, the *Nyāya* System still describes the sources that lead to invalid knowledge (*Aprama*), detailed in Chart 3, whose recognition is intended to be classified and avoided.

Table 3 - Invalid Sources of Knowledge (*Aprama*)

1. Dúvida (<i>Samsaya</i>)	8. Discussão (<i>Badha</i>)
2. Alvo (<i>Prayojana</i>)	9. Disputa (<i>Jalpa</i>)
3. Exemplo (<i>Drstanta</i>)	10. Raciocínio irracional (<i>Vitanda</i>)
4. Doutrina (<i>Siddhanta</i>)	11. Raciocínio especial (<i>Hetvabhasa</i>)
5. Constituintes da inferência (<i>Avayavas</i>)	12. Resposta injusta (<i>Chala</i>)
6. Argumento hipotético (<i>Tarka</i>)	13. Generalidade baseada em falsa analogia (<i>Jati</i>)
7. Conclusão (<i>Nirnaya</i>)	14. Motivos de derrota (<i>Nigrahasthana</i>)

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The methods presented to obtain information in the mind correspond to: *Anubhava*, experiential knowledge; and *Smriti*, memory, which is derived from the mind and

depends on the *Anubhava*. In addition, it discriminates the form of expression of knowledge and studies the power of words (*Mantras*), as symbols that have the ability (*Sakti*) to accurately designate these objects.

For the *Nyáya* system, acquiring valid and true knowledge (*Prameya*) is fundamental to liberation into life, is the greatest goal of human life, because it completely dispels the darkness of ignorant self-identification and misunderstanding (*Mithyajñana*). The system aims to reach *Tattvajñana* which means "knowing reality as completely distinct from unreality" (TIGUNAIT, 2011, p. 97, our translation).

Essentially logical, it adopts the concept of God or Absolute as Supreme Intelligence, since, by its causal theory, things cannot be the cause of themselves. The *Nyáya* school considers valid and accept the testimony of the great scholars (*Rishis*) who have experienced the Truth in themselves and who confirm the existence of the divine Consciousness.

2.5.2 VAISHÊSHIKA: ANALYSIS OF THE ASPECTS OF REALITY

The *Vaishêshika* philosophical school, codified by *Shri* Kanada in 500 bc.C. it is recognized by the introduction of a category of reality called singularity (*Visesa*), so the name *Vaishêshika*. Its main codification was the *Vaishêshika Sutra* by *Shri* Kanada, as well as the *Svartha Dharma Samgraha* commentary by *Shri* Prashasta Pada, *Udayana Kiranavali* and *Sridhara Nyáyakandali*.

The *Vaishêshika* system presents the concept of *Paramanu* (atom) and the atomic theory of existence, according to which the whole universe is composed of eternal and uncreated atoms, which are governed according to cosmic laws and cannot be divided or destroyed. Although different from the atomic theory of modern science and materialistic philosophy, which is based on mechanical laws and considers an atom that can be transformed, it can be said that the *Vaishêshika* school was the basis for the formulation of it.

In this sense, from the perspective of singularity, the *Vaishêshika* system describes the seven categories of reality, demonstrated in Table 4, according to which the manifest and unmanifest world can be understood. Reality can be described from singularity, the smallest indestructible part of which everything is created.

Allied to the *Sámkhyá* and *Nyáya* systems, these schools defend the liberation achieved through rational, logical, correct knowledge of reality and define that ignorance is the root of all suffering and misery. For this reason, they are recognized as "realistic" schools (LORENZEN and SOLÍS, 2003, p. 170).

It is also important to note that the adoption of terms from similar philosophical schools is the result of the maturing of the Structure of Hindu philosophical thought, which has remained unchanged since Vedic times, and indicate the association of thought structures to achieve the same universal Truth.

Table 4 - Categories of reality

1. Substância (<i>Dravya</i>)	(Quadro 5)
2. Qualidade (<i>Guna</i>)	(Quadro 6)
3. Ação (<i>Karma</i>) - característica dinâmica da Substância (<i>Dravya</i>), que pode causar união (<i>Samyoga</i>) ou desunião.	Movimento físico: 3.1. Para cima 3.2. Para baixo 3.3. Para dentro 3.4. Para fora 3.5. Linear
4. Generalidade (<i>Samanya</i>) - característica abstrata, singular e eterna (<i>Nitya</i>).	Mais alto: existência ou estado de ser (<i>Satta</i>), é todo-penetrante e nada está excluído. Mais baixo: referência limitada (Ex: nacionalidade) Intermediário: conceito geral (Ex: substancialidade)
5. Singularidade (<i>Visesa</i>)	Distingue uma coisa de outra coisa, mesmo se existente ou não existente, oposto de generalidade.
6. Inerência (<i>Samavaya</i>)	Relação entre as coisas: a) Inerência: relação do todo sempre existente em suas partes, permanente. b) União ou conjunção: relação que pode ser separada, temporária, não-eterna.
7. Não-existência (<i>Abhava</i>)	(Quadro 7)

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

Of the seven categories of reality, the first two - Substance and Quality - are more detailed in *Vaishêshika*, from which the other categories can be perceived and understood. The Substance (*Dravya*), detailed in Table 5, is the basis on which quality or action may exist, the material cause from which things are composed.

Table 5 - Types of Substances (*Dravya*)

1. Terra (<i>Prithivi</i>)	Relacionado ao cheiro e ao nariz	Podem ser percebidas pela faculdade dos sentidos.
2. Água (<i>Jala</i>)	Relacionado ao gosto e à boca	
3. Fogo (<i>Agni</i>)	Relacionado à visão e aos olhos	
4. Ar (<i>Vayú</i>)	Relacionado ao toque e à pele	
5. Éter (<i>Akasha</i>)	Relacionado a audição e aos ouvidos	
6. Tempo	Inferido pelos conceitos de agora, hoje, ontem etc.	Imperceptíveis, únicas, eternas. <i>Upadhis</i> : condição limitada.
7. Direção	Inferido pelos conceitos de perto, longe, aqui, ali, este lado etc.	
8. Alma (<i>Atman</i>)	8.1. Individual (<i>Jivatman</i>) 8.2. Supremo (<i>Paramatman</i> ou <i>Iswara</i>)	Eterna e todo-penetrante, possuidor da consciência.
9. Mente (<i>Manas</i>)	Percepção da alma individual, inferida pelas faculdades externas e internas dos sentidos.	Atômica e indivisível. Ordena as percepções dos sentidos.

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The Substance (*Dravya*) is also defined by qualities or *Gunas*, detailed in Chart 6, which circumscribes the universe of characteristics that allows it to be recognized, described, quantified or dimensioned. The concept of *Guna* for the *Vaishêshika* system is not identical to that of the *Sámkhyá*, which is applied to the characterization of *Prakriti* (Primordial Nature).

Table 6 - Types of Qualities (*Gunas*) of reality

1. Cor (<i>Rupa</i>)	1.1. Branco 1.2. Preto 1.3. Vermelho 1.4. Azul 1.5. Amarelo 1.6. Verde
2. Sabor (<i>Rasa</i>)	2.1. Doce 2.2. Salgado 2.3. Picante 2.4. Pungente 2.5. Adstringente 2.6. Azedo
3. Cheiro (<i>Gandha</i>)	3.1. Bom 3.2. Ruim
4. Toque (<i>Sparása</i>)	4.1. Quente 4.2. Frio 4.3. Nem quente, nem frio
5. Som (<i>Sábda</i>)	5.1. Inarticulado (<i>Dhvani</i>) 5.2. Articulado (<i>Varna</i>)
6. Número (<i>Sámkhyá</i>)	Qualidade que pode ser contada
7. Magnitude (<i>Parimana</i>)	7.1. Extremamente grande 7.2. Grande 7.3. Pequeno 7.4. Extremamente pequeno (átomo)
8. Distinção (<i>Prthaktva</i>)	Saber que algo é diferente de outro
9. União, conjugação (<i>Samyoga</i>)	Existência de duas ou mais coisas em um lugar (no mesmo espaço e tempo)
10. Separação, disjunção (<i>Bibhaga</i>)	Saber que algo não está próximo de outro (no mesmo espaço e tempo)
11. Longe (<i>Paratva</i>)	Qualidade espacial de afastamento
12. Perto (<i>Aparatva</i>)	Qualidade espacial de proximidade
13. Cognição (<i>Buddhi</i>)	Refere-se ao conhecimento
14. Prazer (<i>Sukha</i>)	Experiência favorável da mente
15. Dor (<i>Dukha</i>)	Experiência não favorável da mente
16. Desejo (<i>Ichha</i>)	Impulso por atrair
17. Aversão (<i>Dvesa</i>)	Impulso por repelir
18. Esforço (<i>Prayatna</i>)	18.1. Esforço para algo (<i>Pravrtti</i>) 18.2. Esforço contra algo (<i>Nirvrtti</i>) 18.3. Função vital (<i>Jivanayoni</i>)
19. Peso (<i>Gurutva</i>)	Capacidade de cair
20. Fluidez (<i>Dravatva</i>)	Capacidade de fluir
21. Viscosidade (<i>Sneha</i>)	Capacidade de adaptar em formas
22. Tendência (<i>Samskara</i>)	22.1. Atividade: manter em movimento (<i>Vega</i>) 22.2. Elasticidade: tender ao equilíbrio quando em distúrbio (<i>Sthitisthapakatva</i>) 22.3. Impressão mental: lembrar, reconhecer (<i>Bhavana</i>).
23. Virtude ou mérito (<i>Dharma</i>)	Sempre está de acordo com a consciência e leva à felicidade.
24. Não-virtude ou demérito (<i>Adharma</i>)	Sempre em desacordo com a consciência, leva ao sofrimento.

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

To understand its existence, the *Vaishêshika* school also details the category of Non-existence, according to Table 7, as part of the discrimination process. This aspect shows that the Hindu *Dárshanas* are interested in knowing the secret of the manifest world and the unmanifest, and not of a limited portion of material existence.

These philosophical systems can be understood more clearly by current Western science, which has reached theoretical and practical conclusions about matter and antimatter, the consequences of which for the manifestation were already described in numerous ancient Hindu texts.

Table 7 - Quality of Non-existence (*Abhava*)

1. Falta de algo (<i>Samsargabhava</i>)	1.1. Não-existência antecedente (<i>Pragbhava</i>): antes de sua criação, tem um fim.
	1.2. Não existência após sua destruição (<i>Pradhvamsabhava</i>): tem um início, mas não tem fim, existência não pode ser constituída.
	1.3. Absoluta não-existência (<i>Atyantabhava</i>)
2. Mutua não-existência (<i>Anyonyabhava</i>):	Quando duas coisas se excluem mutuamente.

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The theory of manifestation according to the *Vaishêshika* system is described from the concept of singularity or atom, whose specific arrangement and composition generates from the smallest to the largest perceptible object, with souls (*Atman*) who, according to the Law of *Karma*[13], in time, space and direction, have come to suffer or appreciate the world, according to their merit or demerit. Thus, it explains the relationship between beings and manifestation (TIGUNAT, 2011).

Such findings of the *Vaishêshika* school expose its scientific and spiritual character regarding the manifestation, life and universal laws.

2.5.3 SÁMKHYÁ: DUALIST THEORY

The oldest system of the Hindu tradition, the *Sámkhyá* school of naturalistic philosophy influenced philosophical systems around the world (LORENZEN and

SOLÍS , 2003, p. 165). Its main coder was the sage *Shri Kapila*, who introduced him to the *Sámkhyá Sutra* as the "Philosophy of Creation" in 600 BC.C. The *Sámkhyá-Kariká* (200 d.C.) by *Iswarakrishna* is the most recent text available (GAMA, 2011, p. 78).

The Sanskrit word *Sámkhyá* is formed from the syllables "Sam", which means "correct, correct, discriminative" and "Khya" meaning "knowledge", can thus be translated as "knowledge of discrimination", "enumeration, analysis, number or account". It presents in an enumerative way the theory of manifestation or causation in twenty-four principles or *Tattvas*, in which the *Purusha* (Spiritual I) and *Prakriti* (Primordial Nature) constitute the primordial source of evolution, *Bhur* being the manifest world from the interaction of both. They represent the duality that generates existence and in *Samádhi* (Enlightenment of Consciousness) this dualism is transcended and only the reality of *Purusha* is perceived (self-perceived). A set of logical tests for the existence of *Purusha* is associated with the theory of causation, as explained in Chart 8.

Table 8 - Evidence of *Sámkhyá* cosmology

Teoria da Causação	Existência do <i>Purusha</i>
1. <i>Asadakaranat</i> : efeito existe na causa material antes de sua produção. Ninguém pode produzir um efeito no qual a causa ainda não exista.	1. Todos os objetos do mundo são destinados a serem utilizados. Objetos não podem usufruir de sua própria existência. O apreciador é o <i>Purusha</i> .
2. <i>Upadanagrahanat</i> : devido a relação invariável entre causa e efeito, causa material pode produzir apenas o efeito a que é relacionado.	2. Não se pode dizer que os objetos são destinados por <i>Prakriti</i> , pois é inconsciente e é sua a causa material; não pode ser seu próprio desfrutador. O usufruidor é um ser consciente que não possui os 3 <i>Gunas</i> .
3. <i>Sarvasambhavabhavat</i> : As coisas não podem ser produzidas de qualquer coisa ou em qualquer lugar. Efeito existe em causas particulares.	3. Todos os objetos do mundo externo são inconscientes, não podem funcionar sem um guia consciente. <i>Purusha</i> guia <i>Prakriti</i> e sua manifestação.
4. <i>Saktasya-sakya-karanat</i> : efeito existe na causa de forma imanifesta antes de ser produzido. Só uma causa potente pode manifestar um efeito desejado.	4. <i>Prakriti</i> e sua evolução não tem sentido e significado se não for experienciado por uma força inteligente. O experienciador é o <i>Purusha</i> .
5. <i>Karanabhavat</i> : se o efeito não existe na causa, algo não-existente não pode se tornar existente do nada.	5. Todo ser humano quer se ater a liberação da dor e da miséria, mas tudo que deriva de <i>Prakriti</i> traz dor e miséria. O princípio consciente que se esforça para liberação é o <i>Purusha</i> .

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The *Satkaryavada* is the doctrine of the pre-existence of the effect on the manifest cause, so that for the effect to manifest a specific arrangement of causes is necessary (SARASWATI, 2008, p. 04). *Prakriti* is the unconscious principle, the Matrix that contains all possible phenomena, and, due to the proximity of *Purusha*, is dynamic by beginning creation (HENRIQUES, 2001, p. 62).

In the event that it can be effectively the Primordial Cause, It is necessary that *Prakriti* be itself manifest, since any manifestation on her part would be a phenomenon caused, an effect, and not the true cause itself. Furthermore, it is admitted that the effects come from compound causes.

According to a Hindu commentator, Shri S.M. Pandit Joshi, "*Prakriti* evolution is a spectacle for *Purusha*; it is through the spirit that human matter must become aware

and achieve the same degree of perfection as the spirit" (In: HENRIQUES, 2001, p. 62).

According to Saraswati (2008, p. 05), everything emanates from Prakriti has the characteristics (*Visesa*) of *Preeti* (Pleasure), *Apreeti* (Pain) or *Usadin* (Indifference), and has the three *Gunas*, detailed in Chart 9. The *Gunas* are the qualities or "strings" that connect the spirit (*Purusha*) to the world, like intertwined threads, impossible to be seen separately. The *Gunas* in dynamism not only generate the manifestation, but also differentiate it in qualities.

Table 9 - Characteristics of the *Gunas*

1. <i>Sattva</i> : leveza e luz (<i>Laghu</i>)	Virtude (<i>Dharma</i>) Conhecimento (<i>Jñana</i>) Desapego (<i>Vairagya</i>) Excelência (<i>Aisvarya</i>)
2. <i>Rajas</i> : movimento e atividade (<i>Calam</i>)	Movimento que resulta na Criação, se manifesta na aceleração
3. <i>Tamas</i> : peso, escuro, inercia, ocultação (<i>Avarana</i>)	Não-virtude (<i>Adharma</i>) Ignorância (<i>Ajñana</i>) Apego (<i>Avairagya</i>) Imperfeição ou incompetência (<i>Anaisvarya</i>)

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The three *Gunas* in equilibrium (*Svarupaparinama*) is Prakriti imanifesta. The manifestation (*Vikrti*) occurs when this balance is disturbed, creating a heterogeneous state (*Virupararinama*). In constant transformation, the vibration, when denser, completes the cycle of twenty-four principles (*Tattvas*) of the manifestation, accurate in Chart 10, this being the most known structure of this *Dárshana*.

Table 10 - *Tattvas* (principles) of the manifestation

(0) <i>Purusha</i> (Espírito)	Centelha divina, consciente, eterna e não criada, livre da limitação espaço, tempo, da dor e do prazer.
(1) <i>Prakriti</i> (Natureza Primordial)	Fonte primordial de toda a manifestação, inconsciente.
(2) <i>Mahat ou Buddhi</i> (Inteligência Manifesta)	“Inteligência Suprema ainda não individualizada. Começo da manifestação e da identificação. Inconsciente funciona como se fosse consciente.
(3) <i>Ahamkára</i> (Ego, Autoconsciência);	Senso do “eu”, Ego ou egoísmo, senso exagerado de auto-importância e cria a entidade individual.
(4) <i>Manas</i> (Mente);	Mestre que organiza e dá significado aos sentidos. Está sujeita à dissolução.
(5-9) <i>Jñanendriyas</i> - cinco órgãos do sentido;	<i>Ghrana tattva</i> : cheiro (nariz) - <i>Ghranendriya</i> <i>Rasana tattva</i> : sabor (língua) - <i>Rasanendriya</i> <i>Chakshu tattva</i> : visão (olhos) - <i>Cakshurindriya</i> <i>Tvak tattva</i> : toque (pele) - <i>Sparsendriya</i> <i>Shrotra tattva</i> : audição (ouvido) - <i>Sravanendriya</i>
(10-14) <i>Karmendriyas</i> - cinco órgãos motores;	<i>Vak tattva</i> : fala (voz) - <i>Vagindriya</i> <i>Pani tattva</i> : agarrar (mãos) - <i>Hastendriya</i> <i>Pada tattva</i> : locomoção (pés) - <i>Padendriya</i> <i>Payu tattva</i> : excreção (ânus) - <i>Payvindiya</i> <i>Upastha tattva</i> - procriação (genitais) - <i>Upasthendriya</i>
(15-19) <i>Tanmatras</i> - cinco elementos sutis;	<i>Shabda Tattva</i> : Som <i>Sparsha Tattva</i> : Sentir <i>Rupa Tattva</i> : Forma <i>Rasa Tattva</i> : Sabor <i>Gandha Tattva</i> : Odor
(20-24) <i>Pancha-Mahabhutas</i> - cinco elementos totais.	<i>Akasha Tattva</i> : Éter - de <i>Sabda Tanmatra</i> <i>Vayu Tattva</i> : Ar - de <i>Sparsa Tanmatra</i> <i>Tejas (Agni) Tattva</i> : Fogo - de <i>Rupa Tanmatra</i> <i>Apas Tattva (ou Jala)</i> : Água - de <i>Rasa Tanmatra</i> <i>Prithivi Tattva</i> : Terra - de <i>Gandha Tanmatra</i>

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

According to Blavatsky (2012), the word *Tattvas* also has the meaning of "principle, essence, reality, true nature, truth, Supreme Essence, Absolute Reality, first principle or fundamental element" (p. 680).

The *Sámkhyá* school explains the sources of obtaining valid knowledge, expressed in Table 11. In the process of awareness, the subject (*Pramata*), a conscious principle that receives knowledge, the object of knowledge (*Prameya*), reflection of

Purusha (Spiritual Self), and knowledge (*Pramana*) are active. (SARASWATI, 2008, p. 2 and 3)

Table 11 - Sources of valid knowledge

1. Percepção (<i>Pratyaksa</i>): observação direta do objeto, necessita da consciência do <i>Purusha</i> , que não tem ação (<i>Niskriya</i>).	1.1. Determinado 1.2. Indeterminado
2. Inferência (<i>Anumana</i>): contato indireto com o objeto	
2.1. <i>Vita</i> : Baseado na afirmativa positiva universal:	2.1.1. <i>Purvavat</i> : baseado na observação prévia uniforme concomitante entre duas coisas. 2.1.2. <i>Samanyatodrsta</i> : não baseado na observação prévia uniforme concomitante entre duas coisas.
2.2. <i>Avita</i> : Baseado na negativa universal, eliminação de todas as alternativas.	
3. Testemunho (<i>Sabda</i>): Contato indireto com o objeto baseado em testemunho experiente.	

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, with our translation.

Ignorance inevitably leads man to suffering and misery. Confusing *Purusha* with the things of the world is considered the great mistake according to this philosophical school (HENRIQUES, 2001, p. 62). *Sthitaprajña* (adept) is one who awakened spiritual consciousness through knowledge about Creation, can discern material things and understand the manifestation from the point of view of logic and reason.

The origin of the *Sámkhyá* dates back to the time of the *Rig Veda*, in which the theory of causality was already expressed. Similarly, the introspective practice of *Yoga* dates back to Vedic rituals. Many authors associate *Sámkhyá* metaphysics with the discipline of *Yoga* as complementary, but simplifications of both systems should not be avoided at any cost (FEUERSTEIN, 1975, p. 125 and 126).

2.5.4 YOGA: PRACTICAL DISCIPLINE

Yoga is the practical philosophical school of hindu tradition that exposes the effective method for expanding individual consciousness and reach of liberation (*Kaivalya*) and enlightenment of consciousness (*Samádhi*) in life. The word *Yoga*, derived from

the Sanskrit root "yuj", means "unite, join, reconnect"; as well as "button, cure, path, remedy, or means"; always related to the concepts of practice (*Sádhana*) and discipline (*Tapas*) (GAMA, 2011).

The main objective is the mastery of mental waves, which prevent man from realizing his true nature (YOGI, 2009). Therefore, it explains about the structure and modifications of the mind, expressed in Table 12, and describes the steps for its command. The *Yoga Sutra* de *Shri Patáñjali* (600 a.C.) it is recognized as its main systematization, followed by the subsequent comments of *Shri Vyasa* (400 d.C.).

Table 12 - Changes of the mind

1. Conhecimento correto (<i>Pramana</i>)	Percepção, análise e testemunho competente.
2. Interpretação equivocada (<i>Viparyaya</i>)	Noção incorreta que não se baseia na natureza real do objeto.
3. Imaginação (<i>Vikalpa</i>)	Obtida através de palavras sem a presença do objeto.
4. Sono (<i>Nidra</i>)	Baseia-se na concepção da ausência (conexões cerebrais).
5. Memória (<i>Smrti</i>)	Registro ou retenção de todas as experiências vivenciadas.

Source: Adapted from YOGI, 2009.

The systematization presented by *Patáñjali* describes the practice of *Yoga* in eight stages, known as *Ashtanga Yoga*, presented in Chart 13, and the first two stages, corresponding to *Yamas* and *Niyamas*, explained in Chart 14, constitute "votes not restricted to social class, place, time and much less circumstance" (*Yoga Sutra* II.31, In: YOGI, 2009, p. 63), correspond to the necessary basis for the beginning on the path, without which it is not possible to proceed.

Table 13 - Ashtanga Yoga

1. <i>Yama</i>	Preceitos éticos com a sociedade, organiza a personalidade.
2. <i>Niyama</i>	Preceitos éticos de disciplina pessoal, disciplina o comportamento.
3. <i>Ásana</i>	Posições psicofísicas, o <i>Yogi</i> é imperturbável pelos opostos.
4. <i>Pránáyáma</i>	Domínio e condução do <i>Prana</i> (energia vital) em seu corpo. O <i>Yogi</i> remove os canais obstruídos.
5. <i>Prátýáhára</i>	Domínio e abstração dos sentidos obtida permanentemente.
6. <i>Dhárana</i>	Concentração da mente em um único pensamento, provocada pela vontade.
7. <i>Dhyána</i>	Meditação ou contemplação, mente inteiramente unifocada, que começa a expandir-se para o estado superconsciente, o indivíduo pode acessar os poderes do universo.
8. <i>Samádhi</i> ou <i>Samahitam</i>	Estado de felicidade suprema em que todas as questões são respondidas e o homem se estabelece em sua verdadeira natureza, uno com a elevada consciência cósmica. 8.1. <i>Sabija</i> : com sementes, de desejo, conexão, em forma latente, consciência do Eu. 8.2. <i>Nirbija</i> : sem sementes, consciência do Eu completamente unida à Consciência Cósmica.

Source: Adapted from YOGI, 2009; TUGUNAIT, 2011, with our translation.

The *Yamas* and *Niyamas* of Yoga are recognized throughout the Hindu tradition, accepted and incorporated not only by philosophical systems, but also by political, cultural, social and religious identity.

Table 14 - *Yamas* and *Niyamas* - Codes of Conduct

<i>Yamas</i> Prescrições sociais	<i>Niyamas</i> Proscrições pessoais
1. <i>Ahimsa</i> : não violência	1. <i>Saucha</i> : Pureza
2. <i>Sátya</i> : verdade	2. <i>Santoshá</i> : Contentamento
3. <i>Asteya</i> : não roubar	3. <i>Tapas</i> : Austeridade
4. <i>Bhramachárya</i> : consciência espiritual	4. <i>Swádhyáya</i> : Auto-estudo
5. <i>Aparigraha</i> : não possessividade	5. <i>Ishvarapranidhana</i> : entrega espiritual

Source: Adapted from YOGI, 2009; TUGUNAIT, 2011, with our translation.

The *Yoga* school also describes in detail the other processes that the mind experiences, mainly because it states that "the pain that has not yet arisen can be avoided" (YOGI, 2009, p. 59). Among them, obstacles (*Vikshepas*) and afflictions

(*Kleshas*), accurate in Chart 15, are of fundamental importance for *Yogi* to understand the impediments in his path. This philosophical system also minucia spiritual aspects developed in the domain of each step, the psychic powers achieved (*Siddhis*), the types of *Samádhi*, with the precision of a safe guide to knowledge of universal Truth.

Table 15 - Obstacles and afflictions

Obstáculos (<i>Vikshepa</i>) - Distrações da mente	Aflições (<i>Kleshas</i>) - Causam desequilíbrio da consciência
1. Doença (<i>Vyádhi</i>)	1. Ignorância (<i>Avidya</i>)
2. Apatia (<i>Styána</i>)	2. Egoísmo (<i>Ashmita</i>)
3. Dúvida (<i>Samsáya</i>)	3. Desejo (<i>Raga</i>)
4. Falta de entusiasmo (<i>Pramáda</i>)	4. Aversão (<i>Dvesha</i>)
5. Indolência, preguiça (<i>Alásya</i>)	5. Apego à vida (<i>Abhinivesha</i>)
6. Apego material, ao prazer (<i>Rágaprakriti</i>)	
7. Percepções errôneas (<i>Bhrantidárshan</i>)	
8. Instabilidade (<i>Anavashtitha</i>)	

Source: Adapted from YOGI, 2009; TUGUNAIT, 2011, with our translation.

For *Yoga*, concentration is the gateway to the *Samádhi*, state of experience of the divine Essence. Without concentration, the energy of the mind is dissipated in vague thoughts, worries and fantasies, and identifies with the things of the world through the senses. In *Samádhi*, *Yogi* recognizes only his *Purusha*, which is not affected by the afflictions of ignorance, selfishness, desire, aversion, fear, and death. Gradually, it becomes free of *Karmas*[14] and latent impressions.

2.5.5 MIMÁNSA: FREEDOM FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF DUTY

The *Mimánsa* and *Vêdánta* systems are closely related to each other, often considered interdependent. It can even be said that the *Vêdánta* has its roots in *Mimánsa* (LORENZEN and SOLÍS, 2003; TIGUNAT, 2011). Traditionally the *Mimánsa* system is known as *Purva Mimánsa*, which means in Sanskrit "initial teaching"; The *Vêdánta* in turn is known as *Uttara Mimánsa*, which means "later teaching". Its main systematization was the *Mimánsa Sutra* of *Shri Jaimini* (400 a.C.), as well as the *Mimánsa-Anukramanika* of *Mandana-Misra*.

The Sanskrit word *Mimánsa* means "to truly understand" or "systematic investigation", which highlights the principle that man cannot rest without understanding his responsibility (*Dharma*[15]) in the world. To this end, he elaborated a sophisticated method of interpretation of the Vedic texts, which illuminate the meaning of rituals, the science of mantras and the practice of meditation (LORENZEN and SOLÍS, 2003, p. 172 and 173).

Although ritualistic, it warns not to confuse with the external aspects of rituals, because "the ritual offers a complete context and opportunity to understand the value of action" (TIGUNAT, 2011, our translation). Therefore, it also teaches *Karma Yoga*, or *Yoga* of altruistic action, to transform actions into rituals and involve life in divine consciousness, which results in the fact that the school is also known as *Karma-Mimánsa* (BLAVATSKY, 2012, p. 192).

For the *Mimánsa* System, the world originated from the vibration of *mantra*, in primary forms, endorsed with perfect happiness, whose cause is transcendent and eternal. The *Mantra* is therefore the knowledge of the Divine Essence expressed in the form of sound and symbolism, experienced by scholars in a deep state of meditation.

The two universal factors are intertwined in an inseparable way in the manifestation: the sound (*Sabda*), as name, vibration and *Mantra*, and the object denoted by sound (*Artha*), with form, archetype and Divinity. Thus, the school classifies two types of sound: with meaning (with phonemes constituting language) and without meaning (not formulated in words). Thus, in addition to the ways of obtaining valid or true knowledge[16] (*Pramana*), the level achieved by communication corresponds to an important object of study of the *Mimánsa* system, described in Tables 16.

Table 16 - Levels of communication (*Vak Shakti*)

1.	Transcendente (<i>Para</i>)	Estado mais fino e perfeito
2.	Concentrada no caminho (<i>Pasyanti</i>)	Estado daquele que vê
3.	Formulada no caminho, pronta para expressão (<i>Madhyama</i>)	Estado intermediário
4.	Expressão com ajuda das palavras (<i>Vaikhari</i>)	Estado mais grosseiro, manifesto e audível, pertence a uma língua específica (diversidade geográfica, cultural, social).

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

For the *Mimánsa* school, universal reverence requires man to take a constant awareness of the Truth in all the circumstances of daily life, the best way of expressing divine consciousness. This philosophical school incorporates knowledge of realistic schools and focuses on deeper study of reality with subtle manifestation.

2.5.6 VÊDÁNTA: PHILOSOPHY OF MONISM

The Sanskrit word *Vêdánta* literally means "the end or conclusion of the *Vedas*", consists in studying and practicing the teachings of the *Vedas*, which is exactly the theme of the *Upanishads* and *Brahmanas*. Its main coding made by Badarayana (500 a.C.), is the *Brahma Sutra* or *Vêdánta Sutra*, see Chart 17.

The comment of Sankara (700 d.C.) receives great prominence, thinker of the Line *Advaita Vêdánta*, with a large number of followers in India to this day. The *Bhagavad Gita*, chapter of the epic *Mahabharata*, is also widely adopted by this school, recognized as an *Upanishad* or an *UpaVêda*.

Table 17 - Brahma Sutras Chapters

1. <i>Samanvaya</i>	Coerência dos ensinamentos dos <i>Upanishads</i>
2. <i>Avirodha</i>	Não-contradição entre os teoria e regras lógicas
3. <i>Sádhana</i>	Significado da realização
4. <i>Phala</i>	Metas da Filosofia <i>Vêdânta</i>

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The *Vêdânta* system, known as *Uttara-Mimánsa*, is characterized by being aimed at those who have a monastic life, assuming that they have already realized the fruits of worldly life, and are dedicated to finding the answers about the universal Truth. In general, they claim that material reality (*Maya*) is an illusory and temporary appearance; and affirm that only the Divine Essence (*Brahman*), and its divine spark *Atman* (soul), should be considered as existing (TIGUNAIT, 2011).

For this philosophical school, the Theory of Causation (*Vivartavada*) argues that the effect is merely an illusory appearance of reality that causes it, and recognizes gradual levels of reality in illusion. Therefore, it is necessary to train discernment (*Viveka*) and devotion through study (*Sravana*), pondering (*Manana*) and application (*Nididhyasana*). *Sádhana* (practice) is focused on meditation and concentration.

In addition, fundamental precepts are presented for the practitioner to start on the path of the various lines of the *Vêdânta*, as described in Chart 18: it is necessary to have calmed the mind, mastered the senses, purified their emotions, acquired positive thoughts, be prepared to follow the masters (*Gurus*) and have an immense desire for liberation.

Table 18 - Organization of the *Védanta*

1. Monismo	Unidade da realidade como um todo
2. Monismo qualificado	Unidade da realidade caracterizado pela multiplicidade
3. Dualista (<i>Dvaita</i>)	Deus e criação como diferentes
4. Não-dualista (<i>Advaita</i>)	Somente Deus existe, <i>Maya</i> é ilusão
5. Dualista-não-dualista (<i>Dvaita-advaita</i>)	<i>Atman</i> igual e diferente de Deus
6. Não-dualista diferenciado (<i>Vishishtadvaita</i>)	<i>Atman</i> com potencial de ser Deus
7. Não-dualista puro (<i>Shuddhadvaita</i>)	<i>Atman</i> como Deus, não como fagulha

Source: Adapted from TIGUNAIT, 2011, our translation.

The concept of freedom or liberation is not as valuable as in other philosophical schools, because for the *Védánta* System the *Atman* (soul) is always free. And, because the prison is the great misunderstanding for man, he says that the awareness is gradual as in the described stages of self-realization (*Mahavakyas*). In the first, only *Brahman* is Real, the universe is unreal; in the second, there is only *Brahman* and nothing else (there is no more denial). In the sequence, it affirms I am *Brahman* (it expands the understanding of the Self); and, finally, it considers that the whole universe is *Brahman* (Divine love for everything) (TIGUNAIT, 2011).

Today, the *Védánta* is the most widespread Hindu philosophical system in India and in the world, being also the first school to arrive in the West.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The bibliographical research carried out demonstrated that the structure of eastern philosophical and scientific thought, especially that developed by the Hindu philosophical schools (*Dárshanas*), based on the ecumenism characteristic of Hindu Culture, predicted philosophical, scientific and religious paths for man to find and describe universal Truth.

It was found that the study of Hindu Culture reveals that, by truly deepening a scientific mind, you will certainly find spiritual answers, as well as, by dedicating yourself to the study of spirituality, you will certainly find decipherations based on

science; for science, logic, devotion, ritual, religion and philosophy are always integrated into the manifestation. The complexity of Eastern thought, explained with the unique simplicity, is undoubtedly one of the main contributions that ancient India left to our planet, and nurtured from knowledge, experience and spiritual and intellectual experience the great sages that our humanity has known.

It was also concluded that the works that explain the influence of the ancient structure of thought of the Hindu tradition present the depth and dedication that this theme requires and evidences the need for continuity, dissemination and expansion of the study carried out.

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APPENDIX - FOOTNOTE REFERENCE

3. The name "*Bharata*" was adopted throughout the Indian subcontinent, now composed of India, Pakistan and Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal and Bhutan, after the reign of King Bharata, which means "he who is able to nourish, preserve and protect" or "the land that loves knowledge." (TIGUNAIT, 2011, p. 04, translation by the author).

4. *Rishi* is a Sanskrit term meaning Elder Sage, prophet, clairvoyant. (GAMA, 2011, p. 239).

5. The *Vedas*, divided into 4 books (*Rig Vêda*, *Yajur Vêda*, *Sama Vêda* and *Atharva Vêda*) are the oldest scriptures that mankind has known, contains the essence of every teaching of the Hindu tradition.

6. The *Ithásas* are the great epics of India, like the *Ramayána* (500 a.C.) and the *Mahabhárata* (1,500 a.C.).

7. The *Shastras* are sacred scriptures. According to Yogi (2011), it means "scripture, a respected word, authority without the need for proof" (p. 243).

8. The Indol Valley civilization was named "Harappeana" because Harappa was the first city to be found.

9. "But the Vedic civilization of the Indo-Sarasvati is not only the oldest on the planet; it was also the greatest civilization of high antiquity, much larger than Sumeria, Assyria and Egypt combined. As far as we know (and archaeological works are still in the early stages) at the end of the third millennium a.C., this civilization was overane by an area of about 750,000 square kilometers." (FEUERSTEIN, 2006, p. 142)

10. The coming of great masters to the West, such as Swami Vivekananda, Swami Yogananda, Swami Vyaghrananda, among many others, greatly expanded the dissemination throughout the world.

11. "Even in the name and title of Jesus we find Sanskrit words, with corresponding sound and meaning. The words Jesus and Isa (pronounced '*Isha*') are substantially identical. "*Is*", "*Isa*" and "*Ishwara*" refer to the "Lord" or "Supreme Being" (YOGANANDA, 2010, p. 282).

12. Sutras are concise phrases or aphorisms that carry deep content, "mathematically and philosophically perfect sentences, guided "by a cord". (GAMA, 2011, p. 245)

13. *Karma* is a Cosmic Law of cause and effect, of action and reaction. All we do, feel and think is *Karma* that naturally generates a reaction. *Karma* is understood to be neither good nor bad and is exempt from evaluation and judgment. (GAMA, 2011, p. 52)

14. See note 10.

15. *Dharma* is a Cosmic Law that means duty, commitment, which must be fulfilled in life. "Essentially, *Dharma* is the complete and inherent order of the universe. The *Dharma* leads fate, partially influenced by human free will." (YOGI, 2011a, p. 52)

16. On this subject, see the philosophical school Nyáya.

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